

SUBJECT CHARACTERIZATION FORM

Name: _____

1. Academic degree:

- Ph.D. Degree
- Ph.D. Student
- Master Degree
- Master Student
- Bachelor Degree
- Undergraduate Student

2. Your current occupation is in:

- Academia - Time (in years): _____
- Industry - Time (in years): _____
- Academia and Industry - Time (in years): _____

3. Please fill out your level of experience with SOFTWARE PROCESSES.

Please check all the options that apply.

- None (if you choose this option, please do not choose any other one)
- I have a superficial knowledge about this topic
- I have a good knowledge about this topic
- I studied this topic in a course/discipline
- I studied this topic by reading one or more books
- I used my knowledge about this topic in the context of a course in practice
- I used my knowledge about this topic in personal projects
- I used my knowledge about this topic in industry projects

4. Please fill out your level of experience with PROVENANCE.

Please check all the options that apply.

- None (if you choose this option, please do not choose any other one)
- I have a superficial knowledge about this topic
- I have a good knowledge about this topic
- I studied this topic in a course/discipline
- I studied this topic by reading one or more books
- I used my knowledge about this topic in the context of a course in practice
- I used my knowledge about this topic in personal projects
- I used my knowledge about this topic in industry projects

5. Please fill out your level of experience with PROVENANCE MODELS.

Please check all the options that apply.

- None (if you choose this option, please do not choose any other one)
- I have a superficial knowledge about this topic
- I have a good knowledge about this topic
- I studied this topic in a course/discipline
- I studied this topic by reading one or more books
- I used my knowledge about this topic in the context of a course in practice
- I used my knowledge about this topic in personal projects
- I used my knowledge about this topic in industry projects

6. Please fill out your level of experience with the PROV Model.

Please check all the options that apply.

- None (if you choose this option, please do not choose any other one)
- I have a superficial knowledge about this topic
- I have a good knowledge about this topic
- I studied this topic in a course/discipline
- I studied this topic by reading one or more books
- I used my knowledge about this topic in the context of a course in practice
- I used my knowledge about this topic in personal projects
- I used my knowledge about this topic in industry projects